

Cover

DECIPHER **Mobile cross-border patient data solutions** **for EU citizens through Pre-Commercial** **public Procurement**

<p><i>When citing, sharing, or adapting this work, please provide proper attribution as follows:</i></p>	<p>Jean Patrick Mathieu, Esther Arévalo AQuAS - Agency for Health Quality and Assessment of Catalonia, Spain.</p>
<p><i>Abstract</i></p>	<p>DECIPHER (Distributed European Community Individual Patient Healthcare Electronic Record) sought the development of mobile solutions enabling secure cross-border connection to existing patient healthcare portals as well as to other solutions for health management. The applications acquired represent a significant step forward towards patient mobility and their continuum of care throughout the EU.</p> <p>According to data reviewed (2011), 180m people worldwide were known to have diabetes, which accounted for 11% of total annual healthcare expenditure and of major co-morbidities. Through the Pre-Commercial Public Procurement, co-funded by the EU FP7 Programme and coordinated by AQuAS, DECIPHER procurers (Fundació TicSalut, ESTAR and Central Manchester Foundation Trust) challenged the industry to create solutions for type-2 diabetes, which could later be applied to other chronic conditions.</p> <p>After three tendering phases, the successful contractors were:</p> <p>NeXtage & Camelot Biomedical Systems - Colibri: cloud-based platform comprised of a mobile app for patients and a web app for doctors. It allows document sharing and patient monitoring and support. Colibri can be interfaced with regional and national personal health record systems. (http://nextage-on.com/ http://www.camelotbio.com/)</p> <p>eResult - OMNIACARE-based DECIPHER solution: mobile app providing multi-language support for health data access, treatment and health monitoring and emergency episode assistance. (http://www.eresult.it/en-us/)</p> <p>GNOMON Informatics – openDECIPHER – HealthDSI compliant solution with Open System – Open source connector. It provides health record access, multi-language information sharing with professionals and relatives, treatment planning and monitoring, emergency support and geolocation, with a focus on patient consent and privacy. (https://www.gnomon.com.gr/)</p> <p>The DECIPHER consortium estimated that the developed technologies could provide savings of up to 24% of actual Diabetes type 2 direct costs.</p>

PRACE-3IP PCP

Pre-commercial procurement for whole system design for energy efficient HPC

Dirk Pleiter, Fabio Affinato, Philippe Segers, Forschungszentrum Jülich (Germany), CINECA (Italy), GENCI (France)

One of the largest challenges in relation to building faster supercomputers is energy consumption. The world's fastest supercomputers consume up to 18 MWatt. However, many high-performance computing (HPC) centres have already reached their limit in terms of electricity budget. Therefore, making supercomputers faster requires making them much more energy efficient than they are today. For this reason, the European organisation PRACE started a pre-commercial procurement (PCP) on "Whole System Design for Energy Efficient HPC".

The main goal of PRACE (Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe) is to offer world class computing and data management resources and services to enable scientific discovery and engineering research. The goal of the PCP started by PRACE is to procure innovative R&D services that result in highly energy efficient HPC system components that are integrated into supercomputers. To allow for a fair comparison of the solutions proposed by different competitors, the project defined four benchmark applications. These applications were selected so that they reflect the needs of several relevant scientific user communities in Europe. For all of them both, time-

AT A GLANCE	
Programme:	Seventh Framework Programme - FP7
Duration:	01.07.2012 - 31.12.2017
Main outcome:	Design specifications for realising interactivity for future supercomputers
Website:	www.prace-ri.eu

to-solution as well as energy-to-solution were determined at the beginning of the project based on state-of-the-art systems.

The PCP is in its final phase with three competitors deploying pilot systems for final testing within PRACE data centres. This will allow the French company Bull, the Italian company E4 and the British company Maxeler to demonstrate the improvements they were able to achieve.

DECIPHER

Mobile cross-border patient data solutions for EU citizens through Pre-Commercial public Procurement

Jean Patrick Mathieu, Esther Arévalo
AQuAS - Agency for Health Quality and Assessment of Catalonia (Spain)

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After three tendering phases, the successful contractors were:

NeXtage & Camelot Biomedical Systems - Colibri: cloud-based platform comprised of a mobile app for patients and a web app for doctors. It allows document sharing and patient monitoring and support. Colibri can be interfaced with regional and national personal health record systems. (<http://nextage-on.com/> <http://www.camelotbio.com/>)

AT A GLANCE	
Programme:	Seventh Framework Programme - FP7
Duration:	01.03.2013 - 01.03.2017
Main outcome:	Development of a mobile solution which enables secure cross-border access to existing patient healthcare portals
Website:	www.decipherpcp.eu

eResult - OMNIACARE-based DECIPHER solution: mobile app providing multi-language support for health data access, treatment and health monitoring and emergency episode assistance. (<http://www.eresult.it/en-us/>)

GNOMON Informatics – openDECIPHER – HealthDSI compliant solution with Open System – Open source connector. It provides health record access, multi-language information sharing with professionals and relatives, treatment planning and monitoring, emergency support and geolocation, with a focus on patient consent and privacy. (<https://www.gnomon.com.gr/>)

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